

Exploring Vestibuloplasty Modalities: A Case Series of Three Patients

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Abstract

Introduction: Vestibuloplasty is a surgical procedure aimed at increasing the depth of the oral vestibule by adjusting soft tissue attachments, facilitating improved oral hygiene. A sufficient vestibular depth is essential to prevent food accumulation and support effective oral hygiene practices. Various techniques can be used to achieve this, including submucosal vestibuloplasty, secondary epithelial vestibuloplasty, and soft tissue graft vestibuloplasty.

Case Presentation: This report compares three different vestibuloplasty techniques: the conventional technique, laser assisted vestibuloplasty and technique incorporating electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty. The primary endpoints for comparison were pain perception on days 1, 3, and 7, and clinical outcomes assessed after 1 week and 21 days.

Results: The results indicated that the traditional technique resulted in the greatest increase in vestibular depth among the three methods. Pain levels reported by patients were comparable across all techniques. The laser-assisted technique offered advantages such as precision, hemostasis, and the absence of sutures.

Conclusion: Our findings indicate that the traditional technique provides the most significant increase in vestibular depth, with all three techniques exhibiting similar pain levels. The laser assisted approach offers distinct benefits like hemostasis and no requirement for sutures, whereas the electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty is straightforward and time efficient. Each technique for vestibuloplasty presents a unique set of advantages and disadvantages and the choice of technique depends on individual patient needs, surgical goals, and available resources.

Keywords: Laser, L-PRF, Pre-prosthetic surgery, Vestibuloplasty, Visual analogue scale

1. Introduction

Periodontal plastic surgery procedures aim to address various issues affecting the gums, alveolar mucosa, and bone, such as defects arising from anatomy, development, trauma, or plaque-related diseases. These procedures not only serve aesthetic purposes but also contribute to maintaining optimal oral hygiene. The oral vestibule refers to the cavity within the mouth, bordered medially by the teeth and gingiva, laterally by the cheek and lip mucosa, and apically by movable and immovable mucosal borders. Vestibular depth is measured either from crest of lip or from coronal border of the attached gingiva to depth of mucobuccal fold.¹ Adequate vestibular depth is crucial for ensuring proper oral hygiene, as a shallow vestibule can lead to food accumulation and hinder the maintenance of oral cleanliness. Additionally, when combined with inadequate attached gingiva, shallow vestibules may result in marginal tissue pulling and gingival recession, exacerbating plaque accumulation,

gingival inflammation, tooth mobility, bone loss, and further gingival recession. Furthermore, an appropriate vestibular depth is essential for the retention and stability of removable dentures.² Vestibuloplasty, a surgical procedure, aims to deepen the oral vestibule by altering soft tissue attachments. Several techniques are employed to deepen shallow vestibules by modifying soft tissue attachments. These include submucosal vestibuloplasty, secondary epithelial vestibuloplasty, and soft tissue graft vestibuloplasty. Periodontal procedures in the new millennium have moved on from being extensively aggressive to minimally invasive. Recent advancements in intraoral surgical techniques include use of lasers with the advantages like greater precision and a relatively bloodless surgical field. In this case report, we compare

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three different vestibuloplasty techniques: conventional surgical vestibuloplasty, vestibuloplasty using diode lasers, and electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty without sutures. Each technique offers unique advantages and considerations, contributing to the growing body of knowledge in the field of periodontal plastic surgery.

2. Case Presentation

Case 1

A 25-year-old female presented to the Department of Periodontics and Implantology with the chief complaint of difficulty in brushing teeth on the lower front teeth region for the past six months, also complained of rapid accumulation of deposits over that area presenting with diastema. On clinical examination, the patient had gingival recession in relation to lower incisors and reduced vestibular depth in the lower anterior area. After two weeks of non-surgical periodontal therapy, vestibuloplasty with conventional technique was performed (Figure 1). Under local anaesthesia, horizontal incision using No.15 blade was placed at mucogingival junction from lower left to right canine which was followed by supraperiosteal dissection up to the desired vestibular depth. The mucosa on the inner aspect of the lip was carefully undermined, following which a leukocyte platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) membrane was adapted and stabilised onto the periosteum at the depth of the vestibular sulcus using non-resorbable 5-0 sutures. In addition, a further L-PRF membrane was secured over the attached gingiva with the intent of increasing its thickness and enhancing the quality of the peri-gingival soft tissues. The raw area over the alveolar bone was left to heal by secondary intention. Coe pack periodontal dressing was placed for wound protection.

Case 2

A 21-year-old female presented to the Department of Periodontics and Implantology, reporting of bleeding from her lower front teeth region for the past 1 year and diastema that was unesthetic. The patient was having non-contributing medical history. Upon examination, visible plaque and calculus deposits were observed along with inflamed marginal gingiva and interdental papilla in the mandibular anterior region. Positive bleeding on probing was noted. Overall oral hygiene was satisfactory except for the lower anterior labial region, where inadequate vestibular depth and a positive frenal pull were evident around lower left canine to right canine. A vestibuloplasty procedure was performed utilizing a diode laser with a wavelength of 810 nm. The soft tissue laser was operated in surgical mode at a power of 3

watts (Figure 2). An initial incision was made along the mucogingival junction from the right lower canine to the left lower canine. Subsequently, all muscle fibers were meticulously dissected, including the labial frenum using laser, and the vestibule was deepened to achieve the desired depth. Saline irrigation was performed, and a coe-pack dressing was applied along with detailed post-operative instructions

Case 3

A 28-year-old male presented to the Department of Periodontics and Implantology, reporting deposition and bleeding from his lower front teeth and gum recession. He also mentioned difficulty in maintaining regular oral hygiene, hindering toothbrush movement. The patient did not have prior dental history. Intraoral examination showed a shallow vestibule and spacing between lower front teeth, with a positive tension test on the lower front teeth. Following phase I therapy, an electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty was planned to address the shallow vestibule. For vestibuloplasty, a horizontal incision was made at the mucogingival junction from lower left canine to right canine followed by supraperiosteal dissection to achieve the desired vestibular depth using loop electrode. The labial mucosa was then undermined. The incision was sutured, and a periodontal pack was applied deep into the vestibule after ensuring adequate hemostasis (Figure 3).

Post-surgical instructions were provided for all the cases, and the patients were prescribed antibiotics (Cap Amoxycillin 625 mg two times a day for 5 days) and analgesics (Tab Ibuprofen 400 mg two times a day for 3 days). Tooth brushing was restricted at the surgical site for the first week, with extraoral cold compression recommended for the first day. 0.2% chlorhexidine mouth rinse was instructed till 4 weeks after surgery. Coepak was removed 10 days after the surgical procedure and the patient was asked to maintain meticulous oral hygiene. All the patients were reviewed on day 1,3 and 7 and examined for pain using visual analogue scale and clinical outcomes were assessed on day 7 and day 21.

3. Results

An increase in vestibular depth was attained by all the three procedures. In the traditional technique described in case 1, significant gain in vestibular depth was observed during the postoperative reviews at day 7 and day 21. Patient experienced mild pain and swelling in the first two days after surgery, with relief starting on the fifth day. Healing progressed smoothly, without scar tissue formation, and there was a substantial gain in vestibular depth. Patients pain perception was measured using visual analogue scale (VAS) on day 1, 3 and 7. When the diode laser was used, patients experienced notable swelling and pain, as well as difficulty eating, for the first 5 days. However, these symptoms improved thereafter. Although the 7-day postoperative review showed a good increase in vestibular depth without scar tissue formation, there was a slight reduction in the gained depth when reviewed at 21 days. The third technique which involved electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty, achieved a vestibular depth gain. Patients were advised to apply an astringent locally, and by the 3rd week, patients reported symptomatic improvement and resolution of scar tissue. All patients experienced pain, swelling, and difficulty eating for the first 5 days postoperatively. The VAS score for all techniques obtained on day 1,3, and 7 is enumerated in Table 1.

VAS score	Conventional technique	Lasers	Electrocautery
Day 1	5	6	6
Day 3	4	5	5
Day 7	2	3	4

Table 1: Pain perception using visual analogue scale assessed on day 1,3,7.

4. Discussion

Vestibuloplasty, also known as sulculoplasty, is a surgical intervention that aims to alter the relationship between the gingiva and mucous membrane. The procedure can involve deepening the vestibule, repositioning the frenulum or muscle attachments, and expanding the zone of attached gingiva.³ It is used to address issues such as preventing further gingival recession, restoring attached gingiva, enhancing vestibular depth, improving plaque control, and boosting resistance to masticatory trauma. Additionally, vestibuloplasty can be performed for cosmetic purposes and to create a better base for dentures in edentulous patients, thereby improving retention and stability. In cases where tension from the frenulum affects tissue around implants, leading to inflammation and recession, vestibuloplasty can help alleviate the issue. The major therapeutic goals of mucogingival surgery are esthetics, treatment of hypersensitivity and prevention of root surface caries. It was believed that an “inadequate” zone of gingiva would (a) facilitate subgingival plaque formation because of the improper pocket closure resulting from the movability of the marginal tissue and (b) favour attachment loss and soft-tissue recession because of less tissue resistance to apical spread of plaque associated gingival lesion. It was also considered that a narrow gingiva in combination with a shallow vestibular fornix might (a) favour the accumulation of food particles during mastication, and (b) impede proper oral hygiene measurement. Hence, vestibular deepening should be considered where patients experience discomfort during brushing and chewing.⁴ There are some contraindications to consider before proceeding with

vestibuloplasty, such as significant bone loss after traumatic tooth extraction, notable bone resorption due to periodontitis, alveolar bone atrophy following tooth removal, and patients with severe systemic illnesses. Careful assessment of these factors is crucial to ensure successful outcomes and minimize risks. Vestibuloplasty techniques are categorized into three main types: mucosal advancement vestibuloplasty, secondary epithelialization vestibuloplasty, and grafting vestibuloplasty.⁵ Table 2 outlines the various techniques of vestibuloplasty.

Main Category	Sub-classification / Techniques
1. Mucosal Advancement Vestibuloplasty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closed submucosal vestibuloplasty Open submucosal vestibuloplasty
2. Secondary Epithelialization (Re-epithelialization Vestibuloplasty)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kazanjan's technique Clark's technique Lipswitch technique
3. Grafting Vestibuloplasty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mucosal grafts (palatal/oral mucosa) Skin grafts (split-thickness / full-thickness)
4. Other Techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laser vestibuloplasty Electrocautery vestibuloplasty

Table 2 : Classification of Vestibuloplasty Techniques

Clark’s technique, introduced by Clark in 1953, is a secondary epithelialization vestibuloplasty method used in cases where there is adequate bone, but the mucosa is either insufficient or of poor quality. The technique is based on the principle that exposed connective tissue surfaces contract, while those covered with epithelium contract less, and exposed bone surfaces do not contract. Proper undermining and fixation of the epithelial flap are necessary to prevent soft tissues from reverting to their original position, which requires some overcorrection. The conventional Clark’s technique has been effective, resulting in a significant increase in vestibular depth with minimal wound contracture and relapse. However, the surgical process is complex, time consuming, and requires a high level of expertise.

In contrast, laser surgery provides several benefits, including precise incisions, a bloodless field, less requirement of local anaesthesia, and shorter procedure time.⁶ It also creates an aseptic environment and eliminates the need for sutures. Despite these advantages, patient reported more postoperative discomfort, and there was a slight reduction in gained depth by the 21st day postsurgery. The high cost of laser equipment and potential hazards associated with its use raise questions about its routine application in oral surgical procedures.

In the third case, using electrocautery was used to compare the healing and VAS score In a recent study conducted by Karas et al. (2023), the outcomes of diode laser and conventional surgery were compared in terms of vestibular depth gain. The study revealed that conventional surgery resulted in a higher vestibular depth gain compared to diode laser surgery. Furthermore, low level laser therapy (LLT) did not demonstrate any significant benefit in promoting mucosal wound healing.⁷

Patients were evaluated on the 1st, 3rd, and 7th days postsurgery. The study found that patients treated with laser reported lower pain and discomfort, as measured by visual analogue+ scale (VAS) scores, compared to those who underwent the procedure with a scalpel. Additionally, the laser group exhibited improved healing outcomes.⁸

Bhullar et al. compared pain perception following vestibular extension procedures using three different techniques: scalpel,

laser, and cautery. The study supported the use of electrocautery in soft tissue procedures, such as vestibular depth extension, as it provided better patient perceptions of pain and discomfort than scalpel and laser techniques.⁹

A retrospective study by Neckel compared vestibuloplasty outcomes using laser and scalpel techniques, finding no significant difference in vestibular height gain between the two methods. However, patient perceptions slightly favoured laser treatment over scalpel.¹⁰

Although most studies suggest that laser techniques offer better patient pain perception and improved surgical outcomes, our findings indicate that conventional technique produced better outcomes. Furthermore, both techniques demonstrated similar levels of pain perception.

5. Conclusion

This case report explores three distinct methods for increasing vestibular depth: the traditional technique using scalpel, the use of lasers, and electrocautery assisted vestibuloplasty. Each method has its own set of advantages and disadvantages. The greatest increase in vestibular depth was achieved with the traditional technique. Patients reported similar levels of pain across all three techniques. Electrocautery was less time consuming as compared to other techniques used. The laser approach offers several benefits, including hemostasis, precision, and the elimination of the need for sutures. Each technique for vestibuloplasty presents a unique set of advantages and disadvantages and the choice of technique depends on individual patient needs, surgical goals, and available resources. When compared to other studies our findings showed better vestibular depth gain with traditional technique and comparable pain score with all three methods.

6. Limitations

In this case report we have compared only one case in each category which provide only limited evidences. Further comparative studies with large sample sizes are required to gather more substantial evidence on each technique's efficacy and safety.

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